

Synthesis of Fluorobenzoates as Possible Pesticides

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A survey of the literature reveals that several halogenated phenyl- and benzyl-benzoates are toxic to mites and fungi^{1,2}. Alkyl esters of 3,5-dinitro-4-chlorobenzoic acid have been patented as fungicides³. No such data on esters of fluorobenzoic acids are available although *p*-fluorobenzoic acid is toxic to mosquito larvae⁴. We have therefore prepared fifteen fluorobenzoates (thirteen from *p*-fluorobenzoic acid and two from 4-fluoro-3-nitrobenzoic acid) as likely pest control chemicals (Tables I and II).

Alkyl Fluorobenzoates.—A mixture of appropriate acid chloride (1*M*) and the required alcohol (3*M*) was refluxed for half an hour. The excess of alcohol was removed and from the residue the ester was isolated by the usual procedure.

Aryl Fluorobenzoates.—These were prepared by the method of Spasov⁵. A mixture of *p*-fluorobenzoyl chloride (0.1*M*), phenol (0.1*M*), and magnesium ribbon (1.2 g.) in benzene (25 ml) was refluxed for 2 hours. After removing benzene, the ester was isolated by a similar procedure.

TABLE I

Alkyl 4-fluoro-3-nitrobenzoates.

No.	R.	M.P. or B.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	Lauryl	158-63°/12 mm.	61%	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ O ₄ NF	64.32	64.48	7.01	7.93
2.	Cetyl	45-46°	59	C ₂₃ H ₃₆ O ₄ NF	67.18	67.48	8.73	8.80

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1. Metcalf, "Organic Insecticides", p. 205.
2. Rosen *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **23**, 149.
3. U. S. P., 2841522/1958.
4. Casida, *Biochem. J.*, 1955, **59**, 216.
5. *Chem. Abs.*, 1940, **34**, 2343.

TABLE II

Alkyl or aryl 4-fluorobenzoates.

No. R.	M.P. or B.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1. Pr ^a	175-76°	57.8%	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ F	65.38	65.93	5.91	6.04
2. Et	65-68°/35mm	69	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ F	65.51	65.93	5.81	6.04
• Bu ^a	96-98°/15	74	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ F	67.01	67.34	6.39	6.63
4. Amyl ^a	138-40°/35-37	68	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ F	68.10	68.57	7.02	7.14
5. α -Phenylethyl	157-61°/35-37	66	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ F	73.41	73.77	5.01	5.33
6. Octyl ^a	105-108°/10-12	69	C ₁₃ H ₂₁ O ₂ F	71.01	71.43	8.10	8.33
7. Capryl	110°/15	61	C ₁₃ H ₂₁ O ₂ F	71.12	71.43	8.21	8.33
8. Lauryl	151-53°/30-32	59	C ₁₉ H ₃₉ O ₂ F	73.69	74.03	9.23	9.42
9. <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	57-58°	56	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ ClF	61.97	62.23	3.01	3.14
10. <i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	174°	53	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ BrF	52.38	52.88	2.63	2.71
11. <i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	102-103°	66	^a C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ NF	50.42	59.77	3.10	3.06
12. <i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	104-105°	61	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ NF	50.64	50.77	3.02	3.06
13. <i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	80-81°	64	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ F ₂	66.51	66.67	3.31	3.43

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